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Performance, privacy, and security issues of TCP/IP at the application layer: A comprehensive survey

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Abstract

TCP/IP is the backbone of modern network communication, connecting devices across the world. TCP/IP at its core is a suite of protocols that enables the transmission of data between computers, facilitating the foundation of the interconnected global network. At the Application Layer of TCP/IP is where the interaction between software applications and the network occurs. The user-centric protocols such as HTTP, SMTP, FTP, POP3, IMAP and DNS facilitate various tasks at this layer such as web browsing, email communication, and file transfer. This comprehensive survey conducted an exploration of the performance, security and privacy issues at the application layer of the TCP/IP. It initiated by providing a background of TCP/IP model, its architecture and the core characteristics, with major focus on the application layer. This paper aimed to discuss the state-of-the-art of performance, privacy and security concerns in TCP/IP application layer. It also proposed future research areas to equip researchers, practitioners, policy makers and the decision makers with tangible knowledge, offering guidance in navigating the performance, privacy and security concerns in TCP/IP Application Layer. It aimed to discuss the current performance, privacy and security research gaps at the Application Layer of the TCP/IP Model. The findings of this research sheds light on the performance, privacy and security issues while suggesting the countermeasures to strengthen and optimize the overall performance, security and privacy of TCP/IP model at the application layer. The paper finally suggests future directions and research areas at the TCP/IP application layer.

Keywords: TCP/IP; Application Layer; Performance; Privacy; Security; HTTP; HTTPS; FTP; SMTP; POP3; IMAP; DNS; SNMP; Telnet; DHCP

1. Introduction

The TCP/IP comprises of several communication protocols that are designed to operate over the internet and other private networks [1], hence facilitating the key operations and services across these networks [2]-[4]. It also ensures end to end connectivity by establishing and maintaining communications between the communication entities [5]-[7]. Tasks such as data formatting, addressing and packet routing are performed by TCP/IP hence ensuring reliable delivery of information to the intended recipients [8].

Many people utilize the established connections through a diverse array of devices which includes the desktop computers, laptops, mobile phones, and tablets [9], [10]. In regard to the vast adoption, TCP/IP application layer gains huge significance since it is user centric with the network [11]. According to [12], the primary utilization of the internet revolves around effective communication, entertainment, and education. It is paramount to recognize the nature of digital era which is very dynamic, where the TCP/IP protocol suite not only facilitates day-to-day activities but also serves as the backbone for emerging technologies. The ubiquity of devices connected to the internet brings about

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diverse challenges and opportunities within the TCP/IP Application Layer, hence it is necessary to have an in-depth understanding of its functionalities, performance, privacy and security issues [13]-[16].

In the recent years, the emergence of cloud computing and Internet of Things (IoT), devices have intensified and strengthened the significance of the TCP/IP application layer [17]-[19]. Over the past ten years, the quantity of IoT devices has surpassed the total global population [20]. It is estimated that by the year 2025, there is an anticipation that the Internet of Things (IoT) will achieve the capability to establish connections between all devices utilized in our day-to-day lives and the digital ecosystem at large [21]. Cloud-based applications rely heavily on efficient data transfer mechanisms to ensure quality user experiences, on the other hand, the multitude of IoT devices add some layers of complexity to the already developed network interactions [22]- [24].

Numerous attacks focus specifically on the application layer hence exploiting vulnerabilities in web servers [25]-[30]. Web servers are openly accessible to the public hence it encounters numerous and frequent interactions from users. The primary objective of malicious personnel is to mimic legitimate and regular traffic as possible, for them to exploit and compromise the application. The most common protocols at the application layer includes the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP), Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) [32], File Transfer Protocol (FTP), Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP), Post Office Protocol version 3 (POP3), Internet Message Access Protocol (IMAP)[33], Domain Name System (DNS) [34]-[38] , Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP), Telnet , and DHCP (Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP). HTTPS is commonly employed to ensure the security of data in transit [39]-[41]. However, potential vulnerabilities exist where the user data may be exposed to the risk of a data breach. This risk arises if the processing code is not adequately isolated from all other components, including the operating system on the host machine.

The need to address performance issues, privacy concerns, and security concerns within the TCP/IP application layer is very important because the application layer serves as the main interface for achieving data interoperability, interacting with various services and systems through the user-centric application layer protocols [42], [43].

According to [44], TCP/IP is the fundamental protocol suite that governs communication on the internet. While TCP/IP has been instrumental in enabling global connectivity, it also poses significant privacy and security concerns. One primary issue revolves around packet interception and eavesdropping. TCP/IP packets are transmitted in plaintext, making them vulnerable to interception by malicious actors [45]-[47]. This poses a severe threat to privacy as sensitive information, such as personal data, financial details, or passwords, can be captured and exploited. Moreover, TCP/IP lacks built-in mechanisms for authentication and encryption, further exacerbating security vulnerabilities [48]-[51]. Without proper authentication, malicious entities can masquerade as legitimate users or systems, leading to unauthorized access and data breaches. Additionally, the absence of encryption means that data transmitted over TCP/IP networks can be easily intercepted and tampered with, compromising the integrity and confidentiality of the information exchanged.

Furthermore, TCP/IP-based systems are susceptible to various forms of cyber-attacks, including denial-of-service (DoS) attacks and man-in-the-middle (MitM) attacks. These attacks can disrupt network operations, degrade service quality, or facilitate unauthorized access to sensitive data [52]-[57]. Mitigating these threats requires implementing robust security measures, such as firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and encryption protocols, to safeguard TCP/IP-based communications and protect user privacy. Addressing the privacy and security challenges associated with TCP/IP is imperative to ensure the continued trust and reliability of internet communication networks.

In this study, it is evident that the performance, privacy, and security issues within the TCP/IP application layer are not isolated issues but interconnected aspects, that is, they are holistic in nature. Addressing one aspect inherently affects the other, hence it requires a more robust and holistic approach to navigate the ever-evolving challenges and the dynamic nature of internet communication.

The paper provides a comprehensive analysis of performance, privacy and security issues in TCP/IP application layer Protocols. To achieve this objective, the paper begins by presenting an overview of TCP/IP protocol suite and its architecture with a specific focus on the application layer. The findings of this survey will contribute to the existing body of knowledge by providing researchers, practitioners, decision makers and policy makers with a comprehensive understanding of the state-of-the-art in performance, security and privacy issues at the application layer protocols of the TCP/IP. This therefore informs the development of robust protocols in the TCP/IP application layer. This paper makes the following significant contributions:

- Contextualizing TCP/IP application layer protocols: The paper provides a comprehensive overview of TCP/IP protocol suite with specific focus on the application layer protocols. This includes HTTP, SMTP, FTP, POP3, IMAP, DNS and DHCP protocols.
- Performance, privacy and security issues in the TCP/IP application layer: The core focus of the survey is performance, privacy and security issues in the TCP/IP application layer protocols.
- Privacy and security issues countermeasures at the TCP/IP application layer: The paper also highlights the countermeasures to the performance, privacy and security issues in the TCP/IP application layer.
- Open research gaps and future directions: The paper highlights the open research gaps in privacy and security issues in the TCP/IP application layer.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section I, II and III provides a concise introduction and overview of the TCP/IP application layer, with the key concepts related to the TCP/IP protocol and OSI reference model. The section also highlights the similarities and differences between the TCP/IP and the OSI reference model. Section IV conducts a comprehensive survey of the relevant literature, while Section V outlines the research methodology adopted for this study and covers sub-sections such as the research questions that guides the study. Section VI presents comprehensive analysis and discussions of the study focusing on in-depth exploration various attacks in the application layer protocols. Section VII presents the research gaps and future directions, finally, Section VIII presents the concluding remarks of this survey paper.

1.1. Research Motivation

The motivation behind conducting this survey lies in the increasing reliance on TCP/IP protocols specifically at the application layer. In today's interconnected world, where desktop computers, laptops, mobile phones, and tablets are commonplace, understanding the performance, privacy, and security issues within the TCP/IP application layer is crucial. This is coupled with the high emergence of cloud computing and Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and the fundamental role of TCP/IP plays in the internet. The article aims to shed light on the performance, security and privacy issues at the TCP/IP application layer protocols, its objective being to provide researchers, practitioners, decision makers and policy makers with a comprehensive understanding of the state-of-the-art in performance, security and privacy issues at the TCP/IP application layer in the rapidly evolving digital ecosystem.

2. Overview

2.1. TCP/IP Architecture

The TCP/IP protocol suite stands as an industry-standard for large networks that are interconnected worldwide [58]. In today's internet, TCP/IP predates the OSI model as it serves as the foundational protocol. Unlike the OSI model's seven layers, the TCP/IP protocol suite consolidates the first three layers into a single layer, application layer and the last two into a unified layer (Network Interface). This distinction results in four layers for TCP/IP: Application Layer, Transport Layer, Internet Layer, and Network Interface Layer [59]. The functions align with the corresponding layers of the OSI model, however, the layer mapping is not one-to-one due to the differences in their architectural development, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The TCP/IP Architecture

2.2. TCP/IP vs OSI Model

The Open System Interconnection (OSI) Model serves as a logical and conceptual framework defining network communication for systems that aim to interconnect and communicate with each other. OSI Model outlines a systematic

approach to organizing and understanding the complexities of computer packet transfer through the use of different layers of protocols. The OSI Model not only provides a blueprint for logical network structure but also effectively illustrates the process of data transfer between interconnected systems, making it a fundamental guide in the field of networking [60], [61].

2.2.1. Commonalities between the TCP/IP and OSI Models

The two conceptual frameworks have several commonalities as summarized in Table 1 below:

Table 1 The Commonalities of the OSI and TCP/IP Model

S/No	Commonality	Explanation
1	<i>Logical Models</i>	Both the TCP/IP and OSI models operate as logical models, providing a structured framework for understanding and implementing network communication processes.
2	<i>Standard Definition</i>	Both TCP/IP and OSI model play a critical role in defining standards for networking hence both contributes to the establishment of a robust common ground for communication protocols and devices.
3	<i>Framework for Implementation</i>	Both TCP/IP and OSI model offer a comprehensive framework for creating and implementing networking standards and devices. They guide the development of protocols and technologies that facilitate effective communication in computer networks. <i>Layered Approach:</i> Both models adopt a layered approach to network communication, breaking down the complex process into distinct layers, each responsible for specific functionalities. This layering enhances modularity and ease of understanding.
4	<i>Functionality Standards</i>	In both models, individual layers define specific functionalities and set standards exclusive to that particular functionality. This approach contributes to clarity and facilitates the efficient implementation of diverse networking functionalities.
5	<i>Interoperability</i>	Both models support interoperability, allowing manufacturers to produce devices and network components that can coexist and collaborate seamlessly with those from other manufacturers. This interoperability is essential for the diverse range of devices that constitute modern computer networks.
6	<i>Simplified Troubleshooting</i>	The division of complex functions into simpler components in both models simplifies the troubleshooting process. This modular approach aids in identifying and resolving issues at specific layers without the need to delve into the entire network structure.
7	<i>Referencing Existing Standards</i>	Instead of redefining standards and protocols already established by organizations like IEEE, both models reference and incorporate these existing standards. For instance, Ethernet standards were defined by IEEE before the inception of these models, and both TCP/IP and OSI models leveraged these standards rather than duplicating the effort.

2.2.2. Differences Between OSI Model and TCP/IP Model

The OSI Reference Model and the TCP/IP Model, although both serve as the fundamental frameworks for network communication, they differ in terms of their purposes, approaches, and development origins. The OSI Reference Model is a logical and conceptual model focusing on open system interconnection, providing reliability and addressing errors at each layer. In contrast, the TCP/IP Model mainly guides how computers connect to the internet and transmit data, handling reliability as an end-to-end issue with the transport layer managing error detection and recovery. The OSI Model has a smaller header size (5 bytes) and follows a vertical approach. It is also exclusively connection-oriented in its transport layer. On the other hand, the TCP/IP Model features a larger header size (20 bytes), and adopts a horizontal approach, and supports both connection-oriented and connectionless communication. Developed by ISO and ARPANET, respectively, they contribute to standardizing hardware and establishing connections between various computer types. The differences are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 The differences between OSI and TCP/IP Model

S/No	Aspect	OSI Model	TCP/IP Model
1	Purpose and Focus	Logical and conceptual model for open system interconnection	Specifies how a computer should connect to the internet and transmit data
2	Reliability	OSI provides reliability as a fundamental aspect	TCP/IP addresses reliability as an end-to-end concern
3	Error Handling	Each layer detects and handles errors	Transport layer is responsible for error detection and recovery
4	Header Size	OSI header size is 5 bytes	TCP/IP header size is 20 bytes
5	Acronym Meaning	OSI stands for Open Systems Interconnection	TCP/IP stands for Transmission Control Protocol
6	Architectural Approach	OSI follows a vertical approach	TCP/IP follows a horizontal approach
7	Connection Orientation	OSI transport layer is only connection-oriented	TCP/IP model supports both connection-oriented and connectionless
8	Development Organization	OSI model developed by ISO (International Standard Organization)	TCP/IP model developed by ARPANET (Advanced Research Project Agency Network)
9	Hardware Standardization vs. Connection Establishment	OSI helps standardize router, switch, motherboard, and other hardware	TCP/IP facilitates connection between different types of computers

Figure 2 The OSI and TCP/IP Architecture

2.3. TCP/IP Application Layer Protocols

The TCP/IP Model application layer combines the functionalities of the application, presentation, and session layers in the OSI model. This is clearly shown in Figure 2. Application layer engages directly with the users and is responsible for initiating transfer of data onto the network. It utilizes software programs for network communication. The presentation

layer also handles data formatting for proper interpretation by the destination device, including tasks such as data compression, decompression, encryption, and decryption [62],[63].

There are various application layer protocols that facilitate the exchange of user information. Examples of these protocols includes Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP), Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) [64], File Transfer Protocol (FTP) [65], Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP) [66], Post Office Protocol version 3 (POP3), Internet Message Access Protocol (IMAP)[67], Domain Name System (DNS), Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP), Telnet , and DHCP (Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP). HTTPS is commonly employed to ensure the security of data in transit [68], [69]. Each protocol possesses performance, security and privacy issues as discussed in the next part. TCP/IP application layer protocols are summarized in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Summary of common ports in the TCP/IP Application Layer

Protocol	Description	Common Ports
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol	80
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol over SSL	443
FTP	File Transfer Protocol	21
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol	25
POP3	Post Office Protocol version 3	110
IMAP	Internet Message Access Protocol	143
DNS	Domain Name System	53
SNMP	Simple Network Management Protocol	161, 162
Telnet	Telnet Protocol	23
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol	67, 68

2.3.1. HTTP & HTTPS

The Hyper Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP) is an application layer protocol that is utilized in the client-server architecture [70]. HTTP facilitates communication between internet web clients hence acting as a request-response protocol, that is between the web browsers and the web servers [71], [72]. When a client initiates a request, the HTTP protocol transfers the request to the server for processing. After the processing, the server generates a response which is then sent back to the client over the network. This is demonstrated in Figure 3.

HTTPS provides robust security measures for data transmission of data over the internet hence ensuring confidentiality and integrity of data [73]-[75]. However, some researchers suggest that HTTPS implementation can lead to increased power consumption [76], [77], which may not be ideal for devices with limited battery life. Researchers also suggest that HTTPS may lack flexibility [78] in some scenarios, hence potentially hindering the performance and functionality. Giant sites such as Facebook and YouTube have widely adopted HTTPS as the standard protocol for secure communication with their users [79]. Therefore, while HTTPS offers strong security benefits, its impact on power consumption and flexibility should be considered when designing internet applications.

The standard HTTP protocol poses a security risk as data transmitted from the server to the browser is not encrypted, leaving it vulnerable to theft. HTTPS protocols helps mitigate this risk by incorporating SSL (Secure Sockets Layer) [80] certificates, or TLS enabling the establishment of a secure encrypted connection between the server and the browser. This encryption prevents potential interception of sensitive data, such as credit card information and passwords, during transmission [81]-[87]. Authentication is also a crucial aspect provided by HTTPS, ensuring that both the server and the client can verify each other's identities [88], [89]. In today's internet landscape where trust and security are paramount, the authentication function offered by HTTPS is very paramount.

Figure 3 HTTP Request Response

Hypertext Transfer Protocol over Secure Socket Layer (HTTPS) provides security measures for data transmission over the internet, ensuring data confidentiality and integrity. The difference between HTTP and HTTPS are shown in Table 4.

$$\text{HTTPS} = \text{HTTP} + \text{SSL}$$

Table 4 Sample Differences between http and https

Feature	HTTP	HTTPS
Protocol	Hypertext Transfer Protocol	Hypertext Transfer Protocol over SSL
Encryption	No encryption, data is transmitted in plaintext	Uses SSL/TLS encryption to secure data transmission.
Security	Not secure, Vulnerable to eavesdropping and data interception.	Provides secure communication, preventing data theft.
URL	Begins with http://	Begins with https://
Port	Default Port is 80	Default port is 443
SSL Certificate	Not required	Requires SSL Certificate for encryption
Authentication	No built-in authentication mechanisms	Supports server and client authentication
Usage	Suitable for non-sensitive data transmission	Essential for transmitting sensitive information such as passwords and financial data.

2.3.2. Telnet

Terminal Network (Telnet) is a standard TCP/IP protocol that facilitates the establishment of connections to remote devices [90]. This enables the local terminal to appear as if it is directly connected to the terminal at the remote system. Telnet serves as a communication tool, allowing users to interact with devices located at remote locations. Network administrators commonly utilize Telnet for accessing and managing remote devices by establishing connections through the IP address or hostname of the remote device [91]. Figure 4 below illustrates the Telnet.

Figure 4 The Telnet Protocol

2.3.3. Secure Shell (SSH)

SSH, also known as Secure Shell enables users to manage and manipulate remote servers on the internet securely [93]. SSH is positioned as a secure alternative to Telnet and it employs cryptography [94] to ensure the encryption and security of all communications. One of its primary features of SSH is the provision of authentication for remote users. SSH employs various encryption techniques, including Symmetric Encryption, which utilizes a shared secret key for both encryption and decryption, ensuring secure communication between sender and receiver. Common ciphers for Symmetric Encryption include DES, AES, and Triple DES. SSH also utilizes Asymmetric Encryption, utilizing distinct public and private keys for encryption and decryption. The public key is used for encryption, while the private key, held exclusively by the receiver, is used for decryption. Notable ciphers for Asymmetric Encryption encompass RSA, Diffie-Hellman, and defence against potential threats like Man-in-the-Middle attacks [95], [96].

2.3.4. SMTP

The Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP) functions as a Message Transfer Agent (MTA) and operates on port number 25 [97]. In the email communication process, a sender or client requires a client MTA to send emails, while the recipient or server needs a server MTA to receive the mail. SMTP plays a pivotal role on the Internet by defining both the MTA client and MTA server. Its primary purpose is to establish the guidelines for the transfer of data between the MTA client and MTA server through the exchange of commands and responses [98], [99]. In essence, SMTP provides the framework for the seamless transfer of emails across the Internet. Figure 5 illustrates the SMTP protocol.

2.3.5. Post Office Protocol version 3 (POP3)

Figure 5 The SMTP Protocol

In the third phase of email retrieval, a pull program becomes essential to extract messages from the mail server and deliver them to the intended recipient. This process employs message access agents (MAA) designed to retrieve data from the mail server [100]. Post Office Protocol version 3 (POP3) serves as one such message access agent, utilizing port

number 110. When a user initiates email access to download messages from the mailbox on the mail server, the client establishes a connection to the server on port 110. Subsequently, the client employs a username and password to gain access to the mailbox, enabling users to retrieve their messages securely [101].

2.3.6. IMAP 4

The IMAP4 (Internet Mail Access Protocol) version 4, operating on Port 993, surpasses POP3 in both capability and complexity. Unlike POP3, which restricts users from creating emails on the server, lacks the provision for separate folders, and doesn't allow users to preview emails before downloading, IMAP4 introduces enhanced features. With IMAP4, users can examine emails before downloading, opt for partial downloads, and exercise additional functionalities like creating, deleting, or renaming mailboxes directly on the mail server. This heightened flexibility and functionality make IMAP4 a more advanced and versatile option compared to the limitations of POP3 [102]-[104]. Figure 6 shows the POP 3 and IMAP protocols.

Figure 6 POP3 and IMAP protocols

2.3.7. File Transfer Protocol (FTP)

Figure 7 File Transfer Connection

The File Transfer Protocol (FTP) [105] is employed to replicate a file from one host to another, utilizing TCP services for the transfer process. This involves establishing two connections between the hosts – one dedicated to data transfer

with port number 20 and the other handling control information with port number 21. The control processes utilize the control connection, which remains open for the entirety of the FTP session. In parallel, the data transfer processes employ the data connection, specifically opened for the file transfer operation and subsequently closed once the transfer is completed [106], [107]. The fundamental FTP model is illustrated in the Figure 7 while Table 5 presents a summary of the TCP/IP Application Layer Protocols.

Table 5 Summary of the TCP/IP Application Layer Protocols

S/No	Protocol	Description	Use Cases/ Features	Security Aspects	Common Ports
1	HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol	Web browsing, data retrieval, content delivery	SSL/TLS for secure connections	80
2	HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol over SSL	Secure version of HTTP with SSL/TLS	Encryption, secure data transmission	443
3	FTP	File Transfer Protocol	File transfer between hosts	Authentication, data integrity	21
4	SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol	Email transmission	Authentication, message integrity	25
5	POP3	Post Office Protocol version 3	Retrieving email from a server	Secure variants available	110
6	IMAP	Internet Message Access Protocol	Access and manage email on a server	SSL/TLS support, authentication	143
7		Domain Name System	Translates domain names to IP addresses	DNSSEC for security	53
8	SNMP	Simple Network Management Protocol	Network devices monitoring and management	SNMPv3 for secure communication	161, 162
9	Telnet	Telnet Protocol	Remote terminal access	Encrypted alternatives recommended	23
10	DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol	Automatic IP address assignment	Security considerations exist	67, 68

3. Related Work

Over the recent years, numerous articles have been conducted in the entire ecosystem of TCP/IP suite. Many researchers have addressed the general performance, privacy and security concerns [108] in the ecosystem of TCP/IP. Authors in [109] investigate vulnerabilities in the TCP/IP header, analysing various attack vectors such as TCP SYN flooding and session hijacking. The primary goal of the paper was to propose effective countermeasures, utilizing an experimental-simulation approach, to enhance TCP/IP header security and assist network designers in implementing robust security measures at this level. Author in [110] investigates and compares the effectiveness of the messaging protocols which includes the MQTT, CoAP, AMQP, and HTTP within IoT systems.

The authors in [111] provided a comprehensive overview and analysis of the various protocols and standards relevant to the Internet of Things (IoT), while the study in [112] compares various IoT application layer protocols through the implementation of a smart parking system. The researchers in [113] compared the application layer protocols for the Internet of Things (IoT) through experimentation. Several surveys have been conducted but focusing on the general TCP/IP protocol suite. The study in [114] Unveils vulnerabilities associated with web attacks and it focuses specifically on Man-In-The-Middle attacks [115] and session hijacking. The paper analyses trends, contributors, and solutions from selected studies spanning the years 2016-2023, shedding light on evolving cyber-security measures needed to address these threats.

Researchers in [32] explored comprehensively recent advancements in IoT application layer protocols and assess the potential research directions at the intersection of IoT and machine learning. The paper provides insights into the

evolving landscape of IoT protocols while identifying opportunities for incorporating machine learning techniques in this context. Authors in [116] provides an in-depth examination of the application layer messaging protocol in the Internet of Things (IoT). It offers an extended review of the messaging protocols within the IoT context. Table 6 shows comparative analysis of the review papers.

Table 6 Comparative Analysis of the Review Papers

Ref	Year	Title	Objective
[114]	(2024)	Unveiling Vulnerabilities of Web Attacks Considering Man in the Middle Attack and Session Hijacking	The paper explores vulnerabilities associated with web attacks, specifically focusing on Man-In-The-Middle attacks and session hijacking. It also analyses trends, contributors, and solutions from selected studies spanning the years 2016-2023.
[116]	(2023)	An extended review of the application layer messaging protocol of the internet of things.	This article seeks to provide an in-depth examination of the application layer messaging protocol in the Internet of Things (IoT). It aims offers an extended review of messaging protocols within the IoT context.
[117]	(2023)	An approach to application-layer DoS detection	This study aims to address the growing difficulty in countering Denial of Service (DoS) attacks, particularly those targeting application-layer protocols such as HTTP, DNS, and SMTP. It proposes a generalized detection approach for application-layer DoS attacks, utilizing a combination of datasets and machine learning techniques.
[118]	(2022)	Survey on recent advances in IoT application layer protocols and machine learning scope for research directions.	The paper aims to comprehensively explore recent advancements in IoT application layer protocols and assess the potential research directions at the intersection of IoT and machine learning. It also provides insights into the evolving landscape of IoT protocols while identifying opportunities for incorporating machine learning techniques.
[119]	(2021)	A survey on IoT application layer protocols	The research explores evolving IoT technology in computer engineering, emphasizing application layer protocol selection. It defines potential protocols and compares their traffic management efficiency in diverse IoT applications based on experimental results. The paper also aims to streamline protocol selection for effective integration in the dynamic IoT ecosystem.
[32]	(2020)	Security of IoT Application Layer Protocols: Challenges and Findings.	This research conducts a comprehensive survey on the security challenges of application layer protocols in IoT technologies. It focuses on messaging/data sharing and service discovery protocols. It also analyses the main threats, Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE), and provides in-depth insights into good practices and measures to mitigate security risks.
[110]	(2017)	Choice of effective messaging protocols for IoT systems: MQTT, CaAP, AMQP and HTTP	The article aims to investigate and compare the effectiveness of messaging protocols which includes the MQTT, CoAP, AMQP, and HTTP, within IoT systems. It focuses on providing insights into the strengths and weaknesses of these protocols to assist in making informed choices for optimal messaging in IoT environments.
[120]	(2017)	TCP IP Header Attack Vectors and Countermeasures	This paper investigates vulnerabilities in the TCP/IP header, analysing various attack vectors such as TCP SYN flooding and session hijacking. It suggests the possible countermeasures, utilizing an experimental-simulation approach, to enhance TCP/IP header security
[112]	(2017)	A Comparison of IoT application layer protocols	Aims to compare various IoT application layer protocols through the implementation of a smart parking system. It focuses on

		Through a smart parking implementation	evaluating and contrasting Application Layer protocols within the context of smart parking.
[111]	(2017)	A survey of protocols and standards for internet of things	This survey provides a comprehensive overview and analysis of the various protocols and standards relevant to the Internet of Things (IoT). The paper analyses IoT protocols facilitating a better understanding of the technologies and standards that play a crucial role in IoT applications and implementations.
[113]	(2016)	Comparing application layer protocols for the internet of things via experimentation	Aims to compare application layer protocols for the Internet of Things (IoT) through experimentation.

4. Research Methodology

In this survey paper, we analyse existing literature on TCP/IP Application layer focusing on performance, security and privacy concerns. The research methodology employed in this study involves a comprehensive review of academic papers, conference proceedings, and relevant publications. The paper employs a rigorous selection process hence providing a holistic and up-to-date overview of the current state of research in this domain. The methodology employed in the study comprises three distinct steps:

4.1. String Searching

On 15th January, 2024, a comprehensive search was conducted to identify relevant research papers for our study, resulting in a total of 497 papers. After removing 266 papers due to duplication, 231 papers remained. Subsequently, 119 articles were excluded based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, leaving 112 articles for further analysis. During the abstract-based screening process, an additional 89 articles were excluded, resulting in 23 articles for in-depth review. After carefully reviewing these articles, four were excluded as they did not align with the scope and objectives of the current research, leaving a final dataset of 19 articles. After reading the full articles, four more were removed, resulting in a total of 15 articles that were ultimately included in the study. Figure 8 shows the selection and screening process.

4.2. Data Sources

The data sources for this research encompassed a selection of renowned academic databases, including IEEE Xplore, Science Direct, Springer, Hindawi, and PLOS. The databases were chosen for their extensive collection of scholarly papers and articles relevant to the study's focus on performance, privacy and security issues in the TCP/IP application layer. Through a systematic search process using specific keywords and Boolean operators such as ("*All Metadata*": TCP/IP Application Layer) OR ("*All Metadata*": Performance, Security) AND ("*All Metadata*": Privacy Issues). The papers were then carefully evaluated based on their titles, abstracts, and keywords to ensure their relevance and alignment with the research questions and objectives. The selected papers from these databases with the corresponding keywords and Boolean Operators are listed in the **Table 7** below:

Table 7 Selected Databases

S/No	Database	No. of Articles	URL	Keywords
1	IEEE	3753	https://www.ieee.org/	("All Metadata": TCP/IP Application Layer) OR ("All Metadata": Performance, Security) AND ("All Metadata": Privacy Issues)
2	Science Direct	2593	https://www.ieee.org/	"Performance, Security and Privacy issues in the TCP/IP Application Layer"
3	Springer	1527	https://www.springer.com/	Performance, Security and Privacy issues in the TCP/IP Application Layer
4	Wiley	19	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/	"Performance, Security and Privacy issues in the TCP/IP Application Layer"

5	MDPI	203	https://www.mdpi.com/	"Performance OR Security OR Privacy AND TCP/IP Application Layer"
6	PLOS	274	https://plos.org/	"Performance, Security and Privacy issues in the TCP/IP Application Layer"

Figure 8 Publishers in the field of TCP/IP Application Layer

4.3. Screening of the papers

This stage involved a rigorous screening of papers identified from the data sources as summarized in Table 4. The screening initiated by assessing the relevance of each paper according to their titles, abstracts, and keywords, ensuring they were aligned with the research area at hand, which focused on the performance, privacy and security issues in the TCP/IP application layer protocols. Papers that met the predefined criteria were subjected to a more in-depth review to determine the suitability for achieving the research objectives and answering the research questions. During this process, research that focused on TCP/IP layer with more aim in performance, security and privacy issues in the application layer were retained for further analysis. In contrast, papers that did not closely align with the research objectives were excluded in the process. This robust screening of papers ensured that not only the highly relevant papers are included in the study, but also valuable papers are included in the study, contributing to the achievement of the research objectives and the credibility of the research findings. The selection and screening process are summarized in Figure 9.

4.4. Research Questions

In this survey, we aim to address five research questions, which includes the current performance issues in the TCP/IP Application layer protocols. It also aims to address the privacy and security concerns that exist with the TCP/IP application layer protocol. The study finally provides the overview of current research gaps and the future research areas that can address the identified concerns in the TCP/IP application layer protocols. The research questions are summarized in Table 8 with the corresponding motivation.

5. Analysis and Discussion of the results

In this sub-section, we present a comprehensive analysis of the outcomes obtained from our research study on performance, privacy, and security issues at the TCP/IP Application layer. The analysis focused extensively on the data collected during the research process, aiming to answer the research questions outlined in Table 8. We examine the results to gain valuable insights into the performance, security, and privacy issues in the TCP/IP application layer. **Table 9** provides a comparative analysis of the review papers.

5.1. RQ 1: Current Performance Issues in the TCP/IP Application Layer

The investigation into current performance issues in the TCP/IP application layer revealed several key areas. Key findings in the study revealed that latency is a prominent concern impacting the responsiveness of user-centric protocols. Bandwidth limitations were identified also as key contributors to slower data transmission, affecting various application layer tasks such as web browsing and file transfers. Others include protocol processing overhead, concurrent connections handling, resource utilization and data parsing and formatting.

Figure 9 The selection and screening process

Latency: Latency is a prominent concern impacting the responsiveness of user-centric protocols. Latency in TCP/IP networks, often referred to as the time it takes for a data packet to travel from its source to its destination, is a critical

performance metric that affects the user experience and the efficiency of networked applications [121], [122]. Factors contributing to latency include the physical distance between communicating nodes, the number of hops (intermediate devices like routers and switches) data packets must traverse, the quality and capacity of the network connections, and the congestion levels on the network. TCP/IP's connection establishment process, involving the three-way handshake, and its congestion control mechanisms, designed to ensure network stability by adjusting the rate of data transmission based on network traffic conditions, can also introduce additional latency [123]-[126]. Reducing latency in TCP/IP networks is crucial for time-sensitive applications such as online gaming, real-time communications, and financial transactions, where delays can have significant impacts on usability and performance.

Bandwidth limitations: Bandwidth limitations were identified also as key contributors to slower data transmission, affecting various application layer tasks such as web browsing and file transfers. Bandwidth limitations in TCP/IP networks refer to the maximum rate at which data can be transferred over a network connection, significantly influencing the performance and throughput of networked applications [127]. These limitations are dictated by various factors including the physical media's capacity (such as fiber optic, cable, or wireless), the quality of network hardware (routers, switches, and modems), network topology, and the protocols used for data transmission.

TCP/IP's inherent control mechanisms, such as flow control and congestion avoidance, while essential for maintaining network stability and preventing packet loss, can also throttle the data transmission rate, especially in high-latency environments or during peak traffic times [128], [129].

Table 8 Research questions

	Research Question	Motivation
RQ 1	What are the current performance issues in the TCP/IP Application Layer?	Understanding the existing challenges will help in identifying areas that require improvement for better application layer performance.
RQ 2	What privacy concerns exist within the TCP/IP Application Layer?	Exploring privacy issues will contribute to enhancing user-centric protocols and addressing potential vulnerabilities in data transmission.
RQ 3	What are the prevalent security issues in the TCP/IP Application Layer?	Identifying security concerns will aid in developing effective countermeasures to protect against threats and vulnerabilities at the application layer.
RQ 4	What are the existing research gaps in TCP/IP Application Layer performance, privacy, and security?	Recognizing research gaps will guide future studies, helping researchers focus on areas where additional investigation is needed.
RQ 5	What future research areas can address the identified issues in TCP/IP Application Layer?	Proposing future research areas will provide a roadmap for researchers and policymakers to guide efforts towards improving TCP/IP application layer concerns.

Additionally, the overhead introduced by the TCP/IP headers further reduces the effective bandwidth available for application data. As a result, optimizing TCP/IP configurations, employing quality of service (QoS) policies, and upgrading network infrastructure are critical steps for mitigating bandwidth limitations and improving the overall efficiency of data transmission over TCP/IP networks [130].

Protocol Processing Overhead: The processing overhead associated with application layer protocols, such as HTTP, SMTP, or FTP, can impact performance. According to [131], protocol processing overhead in TCP/IP networks refers to the computational and time resources required to process the TCP/IP protocol stack layers, including data encapsulation/de-encapsulation, header analysis, and error checking. This overhead can significantly impact network performance, particularly on devices with limited processing capabilities or in scenarios involving high-speed data transmission [132]. Each layer of the TCP/IP model (application, transport, internet, and link) adds its own set of headers to the data packet, increasing the overall packet size and requiring additional processing at each hop along the packet's journey. Moreover, tasks such as the three-way handshake for establishing a TCP connection, the calculation of checksums for error detection, and the dynamic adjustment of transmission rates to manage congestion control, all contribute to the processing workload. This not only affects the latency and throughput of the network but also consumes valuable system resources [133], highlighting the importance of efficient protocol design and the need for hardware capable of handling high levels of network traffic with minimal delays.

Concurrent Connections Handling: The ability of the application layer to efficiently manage and handle multiple concurrent connections can affect performance. Concurrent connections handling in TCP/IP networks is a critical aspect that determines the ability of a network to support multiple simultaneous communication sessions between devices [134]. This capability is essential for maintaining the performance and reliability of web servers, databases, and other networked services that must manage numerous client connections at once. TCP/IP handles concurrent connections through the use of unique combinations of source and destination IP addresses and ports, allowing each connection to be uniquely identified and managed independently [135, [136]. However, the handling of a large number of concurrent connections poses challenges, including increased memory and CPU usage, potential bottlenecks in network equipment, and the need for efficient connection and session management strategies to prevent congestion and ensure fair resource allocation among all active connections. Optimizations such as connection pooling, load balancing, and the use of more efficient protocols like QUIC over traditional TCP can help mitigate these challenges, enhancing the network's ability to handle high volumes of concurrent connections effectively.

Data Parsing and Formatting: Applications often need to parse incoming data and format outgoing data according to specific protocols or standards. Data parsing and formatting in TCP/IP networks are crucial processes that involve the organization, interpretation, and conversion of data as it traverses through the various layers of the TCP/IP protocol stack [137], [138]. Each layer in the stack has its own specific format for headers and payloads, necessitating that data be parsed (i.e., analysed and structured) and formatted (adapted to a specific structure) appropriately as it is encapsulated for transmission or de-capsulated upon reception. This ensures that the data can be correctly interpreted and processed by sending and receiving devices [139]. For example, at the application layer, data might need to be formatted according to the rules of HTTP, FTP, or SMTP protocols, while at the transport layer, TCP or UDP headers are added to manage flow and error control. Efficient [140] parsing and formatting are essential for the seamless interoperability of network services and applications, but they also introduce overhead that can impact performance, making it a balancing act to ensure data integrity and protocol compliance without unduly affecting network speed and efficiency.

Resource Utilization: Application layer processes may consume significant system resources, such as CPU, memory, and network bandwidth [141]. Inefficient resource utilization can lead to performance degradation, especially in resource-constrained environments.

Scalability: The ability of application layer protocols and services to scale horizontally to accommodate increasing loads is crucial for maintaining performance under high demand [142].

These findings emphasize the need for optimization strategies to strengthen the overall performance of the TCP/IP application layer protocols. Table 9 below summarizes the current performance issues in the TCP/IP application layer.

Table 9 Current performance issues in the TCP/IP Application Layer protocols

S/No	Performance Issue	Illustration	Action
1	Latency	Delays in response time for user requests	Implementing caching mechanisms Optimizing network routing
2	Bandwidth Limitations	Restriction in data transfer speed	Employing data compression techniques. Optimizing content delivery networks
3	Protocol Processing Overhead	High CPU usage for parsing application layer protocols	Utilizing efficient parsing algorithms Implementing protocol-specific optimizations
4	Concurrent Connections Handling	Inefficient management of multiple simultaneous connections	Implementing connection pooling Optimizing connection handling mechanisms
5	Data Parsing and Formatting	Inefficient processing of incoming/outgoing data according to protocols	Optimizing parsing and formatting algorithms

6	Resource Utilization	Excessive consumption of system resources	Implementing resource usage monitoring Optimizing memory and CPU utilization
7	Scalability	Inability to handle increasing loads	Implementing horizontal scaling techniques Optimizing load balancing mechanisms

5.2. RQ 2 and RQ 3 : Security and Privacy Concerns within the TCP/IP Application Layer

The identification of security issues of the TCP/IP Application layer exposed various threats including the Man-in-the-Middle attacks, session hijacking, and unauthorized access Privacy concerns also exposed vulnerabilities in user-centric protocols within the TCP/IP application layer protocols. The security and privacy concerns in TCP/IP application layer protocols are discussed in the next session and summarized in Figure 10.

5.2.1. Performance, Security and Privacy Issues, With the Corresponding Countermeasures

Hyper Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP) and Web Applications in Browsers: In our daily internet communications, web browsers play a pivotal role, serving as the primary interface for interaction. The default communication protocol employed by web browsers is HTTP, facilitating the transfer of files constituting web pages from servers. However, this method involves plain text transfers, making it susceptible to intruders who can easily intercept and read the data packets [143], [144].

Figure 10 Common web-based attacks

To address this security concern, web browser developers have shifted to using HTTPS (Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secure) instead of traditional HTTP. HTTPS incorporates a security protocol known as Secure Socket Layer (SSL), which ensures the encryption of data during transmission between the web server and the browser or web client. SSL utilizes public-key encryption to exchange a symmetric key between the client and the server, and this symmetric key is then employed to encrypt the entire HTTP transaction, encompassing both the request and the response. By implementing SSL within HTTP, the data becomes indecipherable to potential attackers attempting to eavesdrop through packet capturing tools. This security measure enables data to traverse even less secure networks while still maintaining its integrity and confidentiality. Figure 10 illustrates the common web-based attacks.

5.3. Security Concerns in Web Applications and Browsers

Caching Issues: Web browsers store temporary files from visited web pages in a cache on the user's machine for quick access [145]–[149]. This cache may include sensitive data like images, passwords, and usernames. If a user's computer is compromised, an attacker could access this information without authentication [150], raising privacy concerns. Regularly clearing the cache and disabling auto-saving of passwords in the browser can mitigate these risks.

Session Hijacking: Session hijacking [151] occurs when an attacker steals an HTTP session by intercepting and capturing packets using a packet sniffer [152]–[156]. Successful hijacking grants the attacker full access to the session, redirecting communication from the client to the attacker. Weak authentication during session initiation makes hijacking possible. Strengthening authentication measures is crucial to prevent such attacks [157]. Figure 11 and 12 show active and passive session hijacking states respectively.

Figure 11 Active session hijacking state

Figure 12 Passive session hijacking state

Cookie Poisoning: Cookies store session information to maintain user states and avoid repetitive logins. However, attackers may modify or steal cookies on a user's machine, compromising personal information [158], [159]. If an attacker gains access to a cookie containing login credentials, they can use it without further authentication. This poses a risk of unauthorized access and potential identity theft. Web Application Firewalls (WAF) play a crucial role in detecting and blocking cookie poisoning attacks by inspecting HTTP sessions and identifying parameters set in cookies issued by the web server [160], [161].

Replay Attack: A replay attack is a type of cyber-attack where an unauthorized user intercepts and retransmits data to the server [162]–[164]. In this scenario, the attacker doesn't just capture the data but can also modify it, leading to potentially different results than what the original sender intended [165]–[169]. Additionally, the attacker may spoof the client's IP address, redirecting their machine to an unintended destination. To mitigate replay attacks, it's crucial for web browsers to implement effective session tracking mechanisms that can discern legitimate from replayed traffic. Figure 13 shows a typical replay attack.

Cross-Site Scripting: Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) [170] is an attack where a malicious actor injects harmful code into a web application or browser, and this code is then executed on the client side [171]. The primary objective of this attack is to hijack a user's session by stealing session tokens and cookies [172]-[176].

Figure 13 Replay attack

One way to defend against XSS attacks is to disable scripts from running on the website, but this approach may limit some features. Another strategy involves strengthening security controls, especially when dealing with cookie-based user authentication. Figure 14 shows the cross-site scripting (XSS).

Figure 14 Cross-site scripting

Domain Name System: The Domain Name System (DNS) is a critical component of the internet that translates human-readable domain names into IP addresses [177]. Attackers may attempt to manipulate DNS records, leading to incorrect IP addresses and redirecting legitimate traffic to malicious servers. There are two common methods employed by attackers: protocol attacks and attacks on the DNS server.

DNS Protocol Attacks: DNS protocol attacks exploit vulnerabilities in the way DNS functions on a network [178]. Three prevalent types are DNS cache poisoning, DNS spoofing, and DNS ID hijacking. DNS cache poisoning involves manipulating the information stored in the DNS cache, providing incorrect name-to-IP mappings and diverting requests to malicious sites [179]. DNS spoofing entails faking the IP address of a computer to misdirect requests. DNS ID hijacking involves impersonating [180] a DNS server and responding to requests, leading to misdirection. Implementing patches and keeping DNS server operating systems up-to-date is essential in preventing these attacks, and DNS Security Extensions (DNSSEC) can add an extra layer of protection. Figure 15 demonstrates a DNS protocol attack.

Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP): The Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP) automatically assigns temporary IP addresses to client machines on an IP network [181]. As shown in Figure 16, an attacker can misuse this by launching a DHCP starvation attack, overwhelming the DHCP server with false requests and depleting its pool of available IP addresses [182]-[185].

Figure 15 Sample DNS protocol attack

This results in a denial-of-service situation where legitimate users are unable to access the network. To prevent DHCP starvation, port security can be implemented, allowing only a specified number of MAC addresses per port, ensuring that the DHCP server can efficiently manage IP address allocations. Table 10 presents a summary of the common attacks at the application layer protocols.

Figure 16 Sample DHCP Server and Client

Table 10 Summary of the common attacks at the application layer protocols.

S.No	Application Layer Protocol	Common Types of Attacks
1	HTTP	Cross-Site Scripting (XSS), SQL Injection HTTP Flood
2	HTTPS	SSL Stripping Session Hijacking
3	FTP	FTP Bounce Attack, FTP Injection
4	SMTP	Email Spoofing, Phishing
5	Telnet	Telnet Bruteforce, Man-In-The-Middle
6	DHCP	DHCP Spoofing DHCP Starvation
7	DNS	DNS Spoofing, DNS Cache Poisoning
8	IMAP	IMAP Brute Force, Email Spoofing
9	POP3	POP3 Bruteforce, Email Spoofing

6. Research Gaps and Future research areas

6.1. Research Gaps

Following the extensive review, our study identified research gaps within the TCP/IP application layer protocols with much focus on the performance, privacy and security concerns. While researchers have proposed numerous security measures to optimize the performance and enhance security and privacy in the application level protocols, significant privacy challenges in this layer remain unaddressed. In this study, limited studies were found addressing emerging technologies such as Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning integration at the application layer. The need for standardized benchmarks for assessing performance, security and privacy metrics was also identified. Closing these research gaps will provide a more holistic understanding of the TCP/IP application layer landscape.

These gaps highlight the areas that require further investigation and attention to achieve optimized performance, robust and secure communication at the application level protocols. The research gaps that were identified and are detailed in Table 11.

Table 11 Summary of the Identified Research Gaps

Research Gap	Discussion
Privacy Challenges	Despite efforts to enhance security and privacy, significant privacy challenges persist within the TCP/IP application layer, warranting further investigation
Emerging Technologies Integration	Limited studies address the integration of emerging technologies such as Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning at the application layer.
Standardized Benchmarks	There is a need for standardized benchmarks to assess performance, security, and privacy metrics consistently across TCP/IP application layer protocols.

6.2. Future Directions

Moving forward, future research in TCP/IP application layer protocol should focus on several key directions considering the identified issues to guide efforts towards robust improvement. Exploring the integration of emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine Learning (ML). Advancements in cryptographic techniques and privacy-preserving mechanisms will be imperative to address evolving performance, privacy and security concerns in the TCP/IP application layer. Additionally, exploring innovative privacy-preserving protocols and utilizing adaptive security measures to counter evolving threats is also an area of future research. This will assist researchers and policymakers, decision makers to navigate the ever-evolving landscape of TCP/IP Application layer.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this survey explored the performance, privacy and security issues in the TCP/IP application layer. It explores the TCP/IP architecture and user-centric protocols at the application layer highlighting the performance, privacy and security issues in each protocol. The identified research gaps and proposed future areas of investigation serve as a roadmap for researchers, practitioners, decision makers and policymakers to address and mitigate these concerns effectively. Moving forward, prioritizing the development and implementation of robust protocols will be essential in strengthening the overall performance, security, and privacy of the TCP/IP model at the Application Layer hence ensuring a resilient and secure network environment for all stakeholders.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares no competing interests that might be perceived to influence the results and/or discussion reported in this paper.

Availability of Data and Materials

Data and materials used in this survey paper are either publicly available or referenced appropriately.

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